

Psychosocial Challenges of Inclusive Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper dwelt on the initiation of inclusive education by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and looked at how this academic programme could fare well in Nigeria. It therefore discussed the concept of inclusive education accordingly. The paper went further to explain the current state of inclusive education in Nigeria by dwelling in the psychosocial benefits and challenges that characterize inclusive education programme in Nigeria. Probable solutions of the identified challenges were highlighted in this paper. Conclusion and recommendations were also given. Some of the recommendations include among other things; increase in the budgetary allocation to education sector; creation of awareness through the media among stakeholders and the public about inclusive education; provision of trained teachers and adequate teaching and learning facilities supply of regular electricity; construction of new physical structures in the schools, initiation of new inspection and monitoring of school as well as probity and accountability in the dispensation of all the paraphernalia of inclusive education programme so as to develop Nigeria children for nation building and national reconstruction.

Key words: *Inclusive education, Psychosocial, Benefits, Challenges*

Introduction

Recent statistics indicates that approximately 72 million children are unable to exercise their right to education due to rising levels of poverty, unemployment and discrimination (i.e. gender, ethnicity, language and disability). There is also an indication that if no action is taken, by 2015, 56 million children will still be out of school (United Nations Organization Scientific Cultural organization (UNESCO, 2010a). The current trend in Sub-Saharan African shows that 23 million of the present 32 million children will still be out of school in 2015, despite the progress being made. This accounts for 47 per cent of out of school children worldwide. UNESCO (2010b) notes that one in every nine of the above statistics is a Nigerian child.

Enrollment rate in primary schools in Nigeria is placed at 68 per cent (Department for International Development (DFID, 2008) of children who are of school going age, 8.7 million are

currently out of school in Nigeria (World Bank, 2010). Five million of the aforementioned statistics are aged 6 – 11 years and do not have access to primary education. This has placed Nigeria as one of the country's most likely to meet the MDGs goals set for 2015 (UNESCO, 2010a).

In the northern part of Nigeria, the number of children out of school is particularly high with the proportion of girls to boys in school ranging from one girl to two boys and even one to three in some states. United Nations Educational Fund (UNICEF, 2007) with almost 52 per cent (70 Million people) of the Nigeria population living below the poverty line (DFID, 2008), girls are often sent to work in the markets or to hawk wares on the streets. Early marriage and teenage pregnancy also prevent girls from going to school. A lot of girls drop out of school before completing the first nine years of primary and junior secondary school education. Forty – three per cent of this drop-out rate is found in rural areas (UNESCO, 2005).

Although, a detailed breakdown of statistics on the number of persons living with disabilities in Nigeria is not readily available, the National Population (NPC) places the persons with disabilities at 19 Million (Taiwo, 2012). The outcome of civil war 1 that ended in 1970 drew the government's attention to persons living with disabilities. This was reflected in the country's first National Policy on Education, Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013). The policy therefore recognized the marginalized and vulnerable in the society, with emphasis placed on the education of persons with disabilities (Ozaji, 2005). Hence, this paper is aimed at exploring into how children with and without disability could be inclusive in the inclusive education, to identify challenges and to proffer probable solutions.

Inclusive Education

One truism which finds expression readily in democratic settings is that "All men are born Equal". It is in pursuance of the realization of such a lofty idea that led to the emergence of the concept of inclusive education. Historically, inclusive education emerged as a result of this clarion call made on the international community by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) to give each child the opportunity to achieve and maintain an acceptable level of learning. At the World Conference on Special Needs Education in Salamanca, in Spain, UNESCO reaffirmed her commitment to Education for all, having recognized the necessity and urgency of providing education for children, youth and adult with special educational needs within the regular education system (UNESCO, 2010).

Significantly, to attain the noble goal of "Education ForAll" (EFA) as prescribed by UNESCO for all states of the world is to do away with all forms of discrimination in the education of children, their background or special needs notwithstanding. According to the European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (EADSNE, 2011), EFA focused world attention on the basic learning needs of neglected groups and on learning achievement rather than on mere attendance. This is important because most countries have groups of children who are excluded and/or underachieve, leading to long-term economic and social consequences for everyone.

Inclusive education represents the latest attempt in the provision of placement option or alternative programmes for children with special needs. The United Nation's Declaration on

Education for all in Jomtien, (Thailand) focused on integration initiative and equity issues for all including those with special needs. To achieve the goal of “Education for All”, the Jomtien conference called on each nation to take immediate steps to implement the recommendations contained in the documents on “World Declaration on Education for all”.

The European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (2011) revealed that subsequently, other international declarations and conventions built upon the call Education for All. In 2000, the World Declaration on Education for All was re-affirmed in the Dakar Framework for Action, which recognized that education deficits restrict social, economic and cultural development, reducing the capacity of individuals, communities and nations. It was also recognized that there was an unequal distribution of education within and between nations. The commitment to Education for all was further developed in the International Conference on Education in Geneva (UNESCO-IBE, 2009). While the UNESCO’s Salamanca Statement and Framework for action on Special Needs Education was adopted in the United Nations Convention on the Rights Persons with Disabilities (United Nation, 2006), in particular article 24 on Education, also provides clear support for inclusive education (European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education, 2011).

Components of Inclusive Education

To ensure a sustainable and successful implementation of inclusive education in Nigeria, the following components are necessary to be on ground, according to Nataala (2012). These are:

- Heterogeneous grouping: all students including those with special needs are educated together in groups with those without disabilities.
- A sense of belonging to a group: All the students are considered active members of the class. In such an environment, students who have disabilities feel welcomed as those without disabilities.
- Shared activities with individualized outcomes: They share educational experiences (lessons, laboratories, fieldwork, and group learning at the sametime). The learning objectives for the students are individualized to meet each student’s learning needs.
- Use of environment frequented by individuals without disabilities: the learning experiences take place in general education classrooms and community work place.

Current state of Inclusive education Programme in Nigeria

According to the Federal Ministry of Education (2008), several innovative policies that address specific needs and challenges of inclusive education have been formulated in Nigeria. These include the National Policy on HIV & AIDS for the Education Sector in Nigeria; the National Policy for Integrated Early Childhood Development in Nigeria 2007; the National Policy and Gender in Basic Education (2007), the Guidelines for the Identification of gifted Children, 2006 and the Implementation Plan for Special Needs Education Strategy, 2007. Data by the Federal Ministry of Education (2008) stated that the population of Nigerian children of school age with various types of disabilities is estimated to be about 3. 25 million or 7% of the Nigerian

population. According to this report, only 90,000 or 2.76% are enrolled in primary school, while a further 65,000 or 1.85% are in secondary schools.

Moreover, the Federal Ministry of Education (2008) reported that the guidelines for inclusive education issued by the Nigerian government, address: (i) the nine categories of impairment/disability and gifted/talented that “have traditionally been excluded from educational opportunities”. (ii) the changes that need to occur to ensure successful inclusion: adjustments to be made to physical infrastructure, provision of special equipment and material, intensive advocacy to mobilize all stakeholders and communities/grassroots organizations partnerships, collaboration and alliance-building; the specifications of the roles of key stakeholders especially, the National and State Ministries and parastatals and other agencies. There are other inclusion strategies at the formal school system and a four-phase procedure comprising, “teacher training as special needs educators, deployment and retraining; and the need for establishment of special education centers in every funding of service, school management structure, monitoring and evaluation. Others include:

- A flexible structure to facilitate responding to the diversity and providing diverse.
- Opportunities for practice and performance in terms of content, methods and level of participation;
- Assessment based on individual progress;
- Cultural, religious and linguistic diversity of learners acknowledged; and
- Content, Knowledge and skills relevant to learners’ context.

Christiana, Heather, Rosemary and Surajo (2018) states that inclusion goes beyond teachers and requires strong commitment of other stake holders such as families and governments. To guarantee the smooth inclusion of children with special education needs and particularly with intellectual and developmental disabilities, a set of practices validated through rigorous research as supportive and unique that can be universal to Africa is wise.

Concept of Psychosocial

The Psychosocial approach looks at individuals in the context of the combined influence that psychosocial factors and the surrounding social environment have on their physical and mental wellness and their ability to function. (UNICEF, 2007)

The early Greek such as Socrates (469 -339 B. C) Plato (425 – 347 B. C) Aristotle (384 – 322 B. C) Maria Montessori (1782 - 1852), emphasized education of children in a conducive environment, whether at home or outside the school (Olusegun, 2007). He also maintained that psychologists such as Binet, Horndike and Hall explored in to education of children by using necessary apparatus, including laboratory where they conducted scientific research to solve children’s problems. Rousseau advocated child – centered educational so teaching and learning facilities as well as school environment should be conducive for learning. Based on the premise, benefits and challenges of inclusive are presented in the subsequent paragraphs.

From the Nigerian perspective, it could be concluded that Nigeria has joined the other countries of the world in the implementation of the Salamanca declaration. Like every other plans, inclusive education in Nigeria has recorded very little success, but facing a lot of difficulties. Some of these successes are:

Benefits of Inclusive Education

Some of the benefits of Inclusion Education in Nigeria are:

- It helps in making Nigerian public to be aware that the exceptional persons could be educated alongside their so-called normal persons, thereby reducing the negative attitude of the public towards the exceptional persons (Ntshangase, Maikana & Cronk, 2008).
- Involvement of parents in the education of their children, thereby having a say in the education of their children.
- It also helps in reducing the effects of inferiority complex on the part of the exceptional persons. Thereby leading a healthy completion with the normal persons, resulting in high academic achievement (Olusegun, 2007).
- It also helps them to have sense of belonging in the course of exploring the social benefits of inclusion. Researchers discovered that the opportunity to interact with peers without disabilities also had academic benefits, because the opportunities to interact with peers without disabilities provided the support and motivation that was required to allow these students with multiple disabilities to acquire basic communication and motor objectives. Thus, it appears that opportunities to interact without disabilities in inclusive classrooms may affect the educational outcomes for students with developmental disabilities (Edozie & Jacob, 2012).
- It reduces the rate of literacy and unemployment among Nigerians, particularly among the exceptional persons, thereby enabling them to contribute their quota towards the development of the local community and the country in general (Olusegun, 2007).

As earlier mentioned, as Nigeria is recording some little success in its efforts to implement the inclusive education, it also experiences some difficulties which hinder the smooth running for the inclusive education programme.

Psychosocial Challenges of Inclusive Education

Some of the challenges of Inclusive Education in Nigeria are as follows:

- Architectural Barriers: What Article 97 of the National Policy on Education (2013) have not been provided are that; architectural designs of school building shall be barrier free i.e they shall take into account special needs of the handicapped e. g Ramps instead of steps; wider doors for wheel chaired, lower toilets e. t. c. in the course of planning and construction of public or private schools, exceptional persons are never considered. Unlike other countries where provisions are made for easy access to any public buildings. Kyauta (2012) also listed the following challenges of Inclusive Education:
- Shortage of electronic power supply: This is a great obstacle towards the achievement of the goals set for the inclusive education programme. Almost all the gadgets or materials that are used for the assessment, diagnosis, teaching and learning e. g. audiometers, overhead projectors, T. V, Video, C. D, and Computers are electronically operated.
- Corruption: This is spreading like a bush fire in the country is another problem endangering the achievement of the goals set for the inclusive education program in

Nigeria. For example, before the money allocated for the smooth running of the inclusive education programme is released a certain percentage would be deducted and this country until it reaches the hands of the executors of the programme and by the time it reaches their hand the money would not be sufficient for the smooth running of the programme.

- Shortage of fund: educational sectors generally are never given enough funds, to function effectively: Article 98 of the National Policy on Education (F. R. N., 2004) also stated that, schools shall be required to arrange regular sensory, medical and psychological screening assessments to identify any incidence of handicap. In Nigeria, even children attending special schools are never properly screened before being admitted, and where the screened before being admitted, and where the screening tools are found, they are either outdated or not functioning.
- The teachers in primary and secondary schools in Sokoto State (Nigeria) were skeptical of the work-ability of inclusive education arrangement in schools. (Isiah & Samson, 2012). He also reported that in Lagos, Sokoto, Bauchi and Abia States where it has been partially facing a lot of multiple challenges. He went further lament that the inclusive education document by Ministries of Education, Social Welfare and Health in 2006 which was meant to be implemented in Sokoto, Kwara and Kaduna on pilot basis has not yielded fruitful result. This according to him was because of problem of personal preparation, pedagogy, curriculum, learning, environment, funding, services, management, monitoring and evaluation. Lack of employability of exceptional students after graduation is another challenge.
- Lack of awareness: Most Nigerians are not aware of special education as a discipline or are aware that a person with disability could be given functional education like his non-handicapped counterpart.
- Lack of teaching and learning materials: Special teaching and learning materials are required in teaching the exceptional children, but in most Nigerian schools these materials are difficult to get due to short of funds. (Taiwo, 2012).
- There are no incentives set aside for the benefits of the teaching and support staff responsible for the implementation and execution of the programme. i.e in terms of good salary (Jumbo), special promotions. This would attract many people into the system. Though a blue print published by the federal government in 1987 mandated all states government of the federation to increase the salary of all special education teachers by 15%. This policy is yet to be implemented. (Kyauta, 2012).

Probably Solutions to Challenges of Inclusive Education in Nigeria.

For Inclusive education to succeed, it is virtually important that the stakeholders; parents, teachers, psychotherapists as well as school aged children, irrespective of physical condition be aware of the new programme. According to Adelodun (2012), even if Inclusive Education is mandated by law, it will never succeed without the enthusiastic support of its

practitioner. He also observed that there is need for change of attitude by teachers, involvement of teacher in the pre-service training and in service training programme.

Joseph (2020) stated that studies have shown that the benefits that inclusive classrooms offer for children with disabilities and their peers. Instead of pulling children out of the classroom to offer them specialized instruction, in inclusive classroom special education teachers come into the classroom. This allows for general education and special to work together in the same learning environment, benefiting all students, who are offered additional resources and support. This support often results in general academic gains for students with disabilities as well as students without disabilities.

It is worthwhile to develop new curriculum which is suitable to be adopted for inclusive education which calls for existing national educational guidelines and the integration of these with other modern and innovative inclusive education modules that could complement the former. Adelodun (2012) asserted that proper planning and teacher preparation for the programme is essential because they are strategies to be used for the teachers, as they should endeavor to utilize appropriate techniques, skills and strategies suitable in the inclusive class set-up, such as collaborative team approach activity and creative problem solving in their classroom. Adelodun (2012) has outlined the following factors for successful implementation of inclusive education:

- There must be adequate funding. The government should make money available for inclusive education.
- Administrative rigidity and flexibility of location should be removed. Also education resources should be distributed equally.
- Societal attitudes should be changed from negative and positive. The society should view the educational needs of the special persons as something very important.
- The government should change funding and policies. They should be the same for both persons with special needs and normal children.
- There should be adequate manpower development to manage inclusive education programmes. Adequate personnel need to be put in place for successful inclusive education.
- There should be adequate restructuring of the curriculum. Also, there should be adequate system to merge special needs education and regular education.
- Practical skills of observation of students, both individually and in group to sharpen the teachers perception, of variation in learning and behavior and to develop their awareness of variations in circumstance surrounding the students such as their home conditions, which may give rise to difficulties in learning in school.
- Appreciation of educational needs of students with developmental difficulties – physical, sensory, emotional, behavioral, learning. The needs of parents and the value of contribution which parents can make to the children’s development.
- Understanding of practical steps necessary for meeting a student’s special needs and ability to adopt the attitude most suited for dealing with his particular difficulties and to

appreciate the need for modification of the school or classroom organization, the curriculum or teaching techniques.

- Knowledge of the range of specialist services available to students with special needs and their families.
- Awareness of the range of career and professional opportunities in special education, the availability of further qualifications in special education and what special education can offer the teachers engaged in it at the highest intellectual challenge.
- The gifted children should be engaged with additional tasks, intellectual creative learning and competition.

Conclusion

This paper dwelt in the explanation of various concepts such as Universal Basic Education, UBE, and Education for All (EFA) which metamorphosed to Inclusive Education (IE). Challenges of inclusive education and probable solutions were also discussed. It can be concluded that Inclusive Education provides a foundation for children with special needs in ways that are not feasible in special schools or classes. In view of the nature and benefits of inclusive Education, i.e. behooves all states in Nigeria to implement Inclusive Education programmes. Inclusive education this requires support to services move towards the child (rather than moving the child to the services) and in the belief that children with special needs will benefit from such integration as opposed to placing in a segregated setting.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing, it is important to provide the following recommendation:

- The Federal Ministry of Education in Nigeria and Non – governmental organizations should embark on an awareness programme aimed at highlighting the benefit of inclusive education in Nigeria. Through the media including radio, television and newspaper.
- Primary and Secondary school teachers should become actively involved in supporting the inclusive education ensuring that the key features of inclusive education are present in their schools and by implementing inclusive education programmes are pivoted towards achieving the overall goal of the academic programme.
- Proper planning and teacher preparation for the programme is essential. This is because inclusive education programme could be successfully implemented if the level of the teachers' competency is increased particularly through pre – service and in – service training.
- Parents' teachers and children should be encouraged at all times, if inclusive education programmes are to be effective.
- Legal and social support needs to be promoted to meet the constraints facing inclusive education in Nigeria.
- Inclusive education services in form of resource room facilities, individualized guidance and help from special educators and psychotherapists are very vital as they can effectively cater for learners' and teachers needs as well as and guide them on adequate modern facilities and conducive environment that are necessary.

REFERENCES

- Adelodun, G. A. (2012). Preparing teacher for inclusive education. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 1(1), 19 – 95.
- DFID (2008). *Factsheet on Nigeria*: Retrieved from <http://www.gov.uk> organizations. fid- June 20, 2017.
- EADSNE (2011). *Participation in inclusive education – a framework for developing indicator*. Retrieved from [https://www.europeanagency.org/publications/e-reports/participation in inclusive education](https://www.europeanagency.org/publications/e-reports/participation-in-inclusive-education).
- Edozie, I. & Jacob, U. S. (2012). Issues and challenges in inclusive education practice. *International Journal of inclusive Education*, 1(1), 182 – 185.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2008). *The development of education: National report of Nigeria*. Geneva: Switzerland.
- Isiah, O. O. & Samson, A. A. (2012). The challenge of implementation inclusive education for children with learning impairment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Inclusive Education in Nigeria*, 1, 192 – 195.
- Kwauta, I. (2012). The state of inclusive education in Nigeria: Prospects and difficulties. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 1(1), 147 – 150.
- Lere, M. M. (2007). *Component of inclusive education*. University Press.
- Nata'ala, G. B. (2012). Pre – requisite for sustainable implementation of inclusive education in Nigeria. *International Journal of inclusive education*, 1, 100 – 103.
- Ntshangas, S., Mdikana, A. & CronK, C. (2008). A comprehensive study of self – esteem of adolescent boys with and without learning disabilities. *International Journal of Special Education*, 2, 75 – 84.
- Olusegun, A. (2007). *Problem for teacher education for primary schools in Nigeria*. Retrieved from <http://www.usca.edu/essays/vol.222007/>. Accessed November, 2017.
- Ozaji, E. (2005). *Special needs education and rehabilitation for beginner professionals*. Deka Publications, Nigeria
- Peter. S. J. (2004). *Inclusive education: an EFA strategy for all children*. Washington DC: World Bank.
- Taiwo, M. M (2012). Exploring inclusive practice: Perspective of Practioners in a Nigerian context. *International Journal of inclusive Education*, 1(1) 115 – 131.
- UNESCO (1990). *World declaration on Education for all*. Retrieved from [http://www.Unesco.org/educational/efa/ed – for all/background/jomtiem – declaration-shtml](http://www.Unesco.org/educational/efa/ed-for-all/background/jomtiem-declaration-shtml).
- UNESCO (2000). *The Dakar Framework for action: Education for all*. Dakar: Online from <http://unesco.org/images/0012/001202/12040e.pdf>.

- UNESCO (2009). *Inclusive education: the way of the future*. Geneva: Retrieved from <http://www.ibe.unesco.org/en/ice/48th – ice – 47 2008/ conclusions/ and – recommendations.Html>.
- UNESCO (2010a). *Global monitoring report*. Retrieved from <http://www. U is. Unesco. Org/ ev. Phd/ ID=7904-201 & Id2 = Do Topic>.
- UNESCO (2010b). *The Salamanca statement and framework for action on special needs education*. Paris: UNESCO. Retrieved from <http://www. Unesco.org/educational/pdf/SALAMA>.
- UNICEF (2007). *Information sheet: Girls education, Nigeria country office, September, 2007*. Retrieved from <http://www.Unicef.org/Nigeria>.
- World Bank (2010). *World Bank Annual Report: Year view*. Retrieved from <https://open knowledgeworldBank.orgs>.